

CLINICAL SIGNS AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA IN MILITARY PERSONNEL.

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Abstract. According to the latest data from the World Health Organization, 1.8 billion people worldwide currently suffer from iron deficiency anemia. The prevalence of iron deficiency anemia varies from country to country, and is largely determined by the social and economic conditions of the countries.

Key words. Iron deficiency, somatic diseases, dental health, caries, social importance, quality of life.

Currently, in developed countries, iron deficiency anemia among women is 12%. It is obvious that if in developed countries this indicator is as follows, then in other countries this figure is much higher. Nowadays, it is no secret to anyone that women with anemia will definitely give birth to anemic children [4,9].

According to the latest data from the World Health Organization (WHO), 1.8 billion people worldwide currently suffer from iron deficiency anemia. The prevalence of iron deficiency anemia is not the same in all countries, and in many cases it depends on the social and economic conditions of the countries. The disease may have age- and gender-specific characteristics[3,10].

In iron deficiency anemia, all parameters except the INR decrease. Iron deficiency develops gradually and occurs in several stages. The first stage is called "prelatent". At this [2,5].

In case of latent deficiency, it is necessary to review the diet and use special vitamin complexes. For risk groups, such as pregnant women or children, the doctor may prescribe iron preparations at this stage. If the latent (hidden) deficiency is not corrected, iron deficiency anemia develops. In case of anemia, it is necessary to take special medications. Treatment usually continues as long as the body needs iron or until the causes of its deficiency are eliminated. Causes of iron deficiency:

Sideropenia syndrome can develop for several reasons:

- unbalanced nutrition;
- stomach or intestinal diseases;
- blood loss;
- increased need for iron.

Due to the latter reason, symptoms of iron deficiency anemia are more common in pregnant women and children.

The risk of iron deficiency anemia is significantly higher for:

- newborn babies;
- children during the period of active growth;
- pregnant and lactating mothers;
- women of reproductive age, that is, women who are menstruating.

One of the main risk factors for iron deficiency anemia is pregnancy. The expectant mother must provide this microelement not only for herself, but also for her child. By the time the child is born, approximately 300 mg of iron, which is taken from the mother, accumulates in the child's body[3,8].

Breast milk is the only source of iron for newborns. If the body of a nursing mother does not have enough iron, then the child will also have iron deficiency. Iron is involved in the formation of nervous tissue, and its deficiency has a significant impact on the development of the baby. During the period of active growth, iron deficiency can develop in almost 50% of children. Girls are especially prone to it when they grow more actively and begin menstruation. All women are prone to iron deficiency due to regular blood loss during [2,9].

[3,9].

The drugs are taken according to the scheme prescribed by the doctor. Usually they are taken during meals - this improves the absorption of the drug. The most common side effects of any iron supplement are: constipation, nausea and abdominal pain. Treatment should last about 3-5 months. Blood transfusion is the newest method, used only in cases where a person's life is at risk. Each such case is discussed separately by the board of doctors. For the treatment of children, it is convenient to use drugs in the form of syrup or drops. For small children, you can accurately calculate the dose with the help of a doctor and add drops to food. Older children can be given syrup. These types of drugs have a pleasant sweet taste, and the treatment usually does not cause problems. To prevent anemia in humans, you can use supplements in the form of syrup or hematogen. When preparing doses for children, it is necessary to calculate them taking into account their weight and iron content. You need 3-5 mg per kilogram of body weight per day. For a complete and accurate calculation, you should

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